

Input Data & Assumptions for Pakistan

Starter Data Kit

Energy system modelling provides key insights on power generation, capital investment, energy imports, costs of electricity generation, and CO₂ emissions. To effectively run the platform, Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) provides free starter data kits which can be further updated, adapted and applied by policy-makers, consultants and academics among others. For the purpose of this study, a starter data kit for Pakistan was developed following the methodology outlined in Cannone *et al.* (2022). All data was retrieved from open-sources and inserted into the data collection and manipulation tool (DaCoMaTool), an excel workbook designed to facilitate the creation of such kit. Access to data is often a barrier for energy modelling in developing countries such as Pakistan, therefore, this study used assumptions when needed.

This data was used to model three BASE scenarios using the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS): Least Cost, Fossil Future and Net Zero by 2050. Please find below, a list of all annexes available in this article.

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Technoeconomic data

Technoeconomic data to determine fuel and renewable technologies capital price projections was retrieved from IRENA (2016) (Annex 1). Similarly, values for Pakistan's electricity transmission and distribution were retrieved from ERIA (2016) (Annex 2).

Annex 1. Capital costs for fuels and renewable technologies Source: IRENA ASEAN REMAP (2016)

OSeMOSYS Code	Technology	Capital Cost (\$/kW in 2020)	Fixed Cost (\$/kW/yr in 2020)	Variable Cost (\$/GJ in 2020)	Operational Life (years)	Efficiency (%)	Average Capacity Factor (%)
PWRBIO001	Biomass Power Plant	2750.0	69	0.0001	25	38	70
PWRCOA001	Coal Power Plant	1300.0	52	0.0001	60	30	75
PWRGEO	Geothermal Power Plant	2500.0	100	0.0001	50	10	70
PWROHC001	Light Fuel Oil Power Plant	1200.0	18	0.0001	50	40	25
PWROHC002	Oil Fired Gas Turbine (SCGT)	1344.0	18	0.0001	50	40	25
PWRNGS001	Gas Power Plant (CCGT)	1000.0	40	0.0001	30	55	55
PWRNGS002	Gas Power Plant (SCGT)	784.0	23	0.0001	30	35	55
PWRSOL001	Solar PV (utility)	1160.0	15	0.0001	30	100	32
PWRCSP002	CSP with Storage	4965.3	120	0.0001	35	33	30
PWRHYD001	Large Hydropower Plant (>100MW)	1539.0	46	0.0001	40	100	50
PWRHYD002	Medium Hydropower Plant (10-100MW)	1592.9	48	0.0001	40	100	50
PWRHYD003	Small Hydropower Plant (<10MW)	2162.0	65	0.0001	40	100	50
PWRWND001	Onshore Wind	2220.1	89	0.0001	30	100	23
PWRWND002	Offshore Wind	2876.2	115	0.0001	30	100	—

Annex 1. Capital costs for fuels and renewable technologies Source: IRENA ASEAN REMAP (2016)

OSeMOSYS Code	Technology	Capital Cost (\$/kW in 2020)	Fixed Cost (\$/kW/yr in 2020)	Variable Cost (\$/GJ in 2020)	Operational Life (years)	Efficiency (%)	Average Capacity Factor (%)
PWRNUC	Nuclear Power Plant	5500.0	138	0.0001	60	33	83
PWROHC003	Light Fuel Oil Standalone Generator (1kW)	1500.0	38	0.0001	20	42	40
PWRSOL002	Solar PV (distributed with storage)	2130.8	43	0.0001	24	100	32

Annex 2 . Capital costs for electricity transmission and distribution Source: ERIA (2016)

Technology	Capital Cost (\$/kW in 2020)	Fixed Cost (\$/kW/yr in 2020)	Variable Cost (\$/GJ in 2020)	Operational Life (years)	Efficiency (2020)	Efficiency (2030)	Efficiency (2050)
Electricity Transmission	204.2666667	4.085333333	0.0001	50	85%	88%	95%
Electricity Distribution	102.1333333	2.042666667	0.0001	70	100%	100%	100%

The CO₂ emission factors used for oil, gas, and coal were sourced from the IPCC (2006) (Annex 3).

Annex 3. Fuels CO₂ Emission Factors Source: IPCC (2006)

Technology	CO ₂ Emission Factor (kg CO ₂ /GJ)
Crude Oil	73.3
Light Fuel Oil	69.3
Heavy Fuel Oil	77.4
Natural Gas	56.1
Coal	94.6

Current Power System and Generation Pipeline Data

The installed capacity for the power generation technologies in 2022 was estimated to reach 41,240 MW (Annex 4) according to data available from NEPRA. Additionally, power plants under construction are aiming to increase 17,832 MW. This includes generation capacity from fossil fuels gas (Annex 5), coal (Annex 6), oil (Annex 7). But also from renewable energy power stations such as nuclear (Annex 8), hydro (Annex 9), wind (Annex 10), biomass (Annex 11), and solar (Annex 12).

Annex 4. Installed generation capacity 2022 Source: NEPRA (2021)

Power Generation Technology	Installed Capacity in 2022 (MW)	PP Life Time
Biomass Power Plant	369	30
Coal Power Plant	5752	30
Geothermal Power Plant	0	—
Light Fuel Oil Power Plant	2791	30
Oil Fired Gas Turbine (SCGT)	1263	30
Gas Power Plant (CCGT)	14387	30
Gas Power Plant (SCGT)	391	30
Solar PV (Utility)	530	20
CSP with Storage	0	—
Large Hydropower Plant (>100MW)	10131	80
Medium Hydropower Plant (10-100MW)	689	80
Small Hydropower Plant (<10MW)	14	80
Onshore Wind	1336	20
Offshore Wind	0	—
Nuclear Power Plant	3530	60
Off-grid Solar PV	41.71	24
Off-grid Hydropower	15.619	40
TOTAL	41240.329	

Annex 5. Installed and Under Construction Gas Power Stations in Pakistan Source: NEPRA (2021)

	STATION	LOCATION	CAPACITY (MW)	PRIMARY FUEL	Year in Service
1	TPS Jamshoro	Jamshoro, Sindh	880	RFO + Gas	
2	TPS Guddu (Unitis 5-10)	Guddu Sindh	600	Gas	
3	TPS Guddu (Unitis 11-13)	Guddu Sindh	415	Gas	
4	TPS Guddu (Unitis 14-16)	Guddu Sindh	747	Gas	
5	TPS Quetta	Quetta, Balochistan	28	Gas	
6	TPS Muzaffargarh	Muzaffargarh, Punjab	1350	Gas	
7	GTPS Faisalabad	Faisalabad, Punjab	144	Gas	
8	TPS Nandipur	Gujranwala, Punjab	567	Gas	
9	Altern Energy	Fateh Jang, Punjab	31	Gas	
10	Habibullah Coastal	Quetta, Balochistan	155	Gas	
11	KAPCO	Kot Addu, Punjab	1600	Gas	
12	Rousch Power	Sidhnai, Punjab	450	Gas	
13	TNB Liberty Power	Daharki, Sindh	235	Gas	
14	Uch Power	Murad Jamali, Balochistan	586	Gas	
15	Engro Power Gen. Qadirpur	Qadirpur, Sindh	227	Gas	
16	Saif Power	Sahiwal, Punjab	225	Gas	
17	Orient Power	Balloki, Punjab	225	Gas	
18	Sapphire Electric	Muridke, Punjab	235	Gas	
19	Halmore Power	Bhikki, Punjab	225	Gas	
20	Foundation Power	Daharki, Sindh	179	Gas	
21	David Energen.	Jhang, Punjab	12	Gas	
22	Uch-II Power	Murad Jamali, Balochistan	404	Lost BTU Gas	
23	QATPL (Bhikki)	Bhikki, Punjab	1231	RLNG	
24	NPPMCL (Haveli Bahadur Shah)	HBS, Punjab	1277	RLNG	
25	NPPML (Balloki)	Balloki, Punjab	1276	RLNG	
26	Korangi Town GTPS-II	Karachi, Sindh	107	Gas	
27	Site GTPS-II	Karachi, Sindh	107	Gas	
28	Korangi CCPP	Karachi, Sindh	248	Gas	

Annex 5. Installed and Under Construction Gas Power Stations in Pakistan Source: NEPRA (2021)

	STATION	LOCATION	CAPACITY (MW)	PRIMARY FUEL	Year in Service
29	SNPCL-I (IPP-2002)	Jamshoro, Sindh	52	Gas	
30	SNPCL-II (IPP-2002)	Jamshoro, Sindh	52	Gas	
31	Anoud Power (IGC)	Karachi, Sindh	12	RFO + Gas	
32	Intl. Steel Limited (CPP)	Karachi, Sindh	19	Gas	
33	Intl. Ind. Limited (CPP)	Karachi, Sindh	4	Gas	
34	Lotte Chemicals	Karachi, Sindh	48	Gas	
35	Lucky Cement	Lakki Marwat, KPK	16	Gas	
36	Punjab Thermal (PTPL)	Jhang, Punjab	810	RLNG	
<i>Under Construction</i>					
	STATION	LOCATION	CAPACITY (MW)	PRIMARY FUEL	Expected Completion
1	Punjab Thermal Power Plant	Jhang, Punjab	1263	RLNG	Dec. 2022

Annex 6 . Installed and Under Construction Coal Power Stations in Pakistan Source: NEPRA (2021)

	STATION	LOCATION	CAPACITY (MW)	PRIMARY FUEL	
1	FBC Lakhra	Lakhra, Sindh	150	Coal	
2	Sahiwal Coal Power Plant	Sahiwal, Punjab	1320	Bituminous Coal	
3	Port Qasim Electric Power	Port Qasim, Sindh	1320	Bituminous Coal	
4	China Power Hub	Lasbella, Balochistan	1320	Imported Coal	
5	Engro Powergen Thar	Tharparkar, Sindh	660	Thar Coal	
6	FFBL Power	Karachi, Sindh	52	Imported/Local Coal	
7	Lucky Coal	Bin Qasim, Sindh	660	Imported/Local Coal	
8	Thar Energy Limited	Tharparkar, Sindh	330	Local Coal	
<i>Under Construction</i>					
	STATION	LOCATION	CAPACITY (MW)	PRIMARY FUEL	Expected Completion
1	Thal Noval Coal Power Project	Tharparkar, Sindh	330	Thar Coal	-
2	SSRL Thar Coal Mine Mouth Power Plant	Tharparkar, Sindh	1320	Thar Coal	-
3	Coal Power Project, Jamshoro	Jamshoro, Sindh	1320	Imported + Thar Coal	-

Annex 7. Installed Oil Power Stations in Pakistan Source: NEPRA (2021)

	STATION	LOCATION	CAPACITY (MW)	PRIMARY FUEL
1	Lal Pir Power	Mehmood Kot, Punjab	362	RFO
2	Pak Gen. Power	Mehmood Kot, Punjab	365	RFO
3	Hub Power	Hub, Balochistan	1291	RFO
4	Kohinoor Energy Ltd	Lahore, Punjab	131	RFO
5	Saba Power Company Ltd	Sheikhupura, Punjab	136	RFO
6	Southern Electric Power Company Ltd	Raiwind, Lahore	117	RFO
7	Attock Gen.	Attock Morgah, Punjab	165	RFO
8	Atlas Power	Sheikhupura, Punjab	224	RFO
9	Night Power	Qasur, Punjab	202	RFO
10	Night Chunian	Qasur, Punjab	202	RFO
11	Narowal Energy	Narowal, Punjab	214	RFO
12	Liberty Power Tech.	Faisalabad, Punjab	202	RFO
13	Reshma Power	Raiwind, Punjab	97	RFO/HSFO
14	Guld Powergen	Gujranwala, Punjab	84	RFO/HSFO
15	Gul Ahmed	Karachi, Sindh	136	RFO
16	Tapal Energy	Karachi, Sindh	126	RFO

Annex 8. Installed Nuclear Power Stations in Pakistan Source: NEPRA (2021)

	STATION	LOCATION	CAPACITY (MW)	Year in Service
1	(CHASNUPP-1)	Mianwali, Punjab	325	2000
2	(CHASNUPP-2)	Mianwali, Punjab	325	2011
3	(CHASNUPP-3)	Mianwali, Punjab	340	2016
4	(CHASNUPP-4)	Mianwali, Punjab	340	2017
5	(KANUPP-2)	Karachi, Sindh	1100	2021
6	(KANUPP-3)	Karachi, Sindh	1100	2022

Annex 9 . Installed and Under Construction Hydro Power Stations in Pakistan Source: NEPRA (2021)

	STATION	LOCATION	Type	CAPACITY (MW)	Year in Service
1	Renala	Renala, Punjab	Run of Canal	1	1925
2	Malakan/Jabban	Malakand, KPK	Run of River	22	1935
3	Rasul	Mandi Bahauddin, Punjab	Run of Canal	22	1952
4	Dargai	Malakand, KPK	Run of Canal	20	1952
5	Kurram Garhi	Kurram Garhi, KPK	Run of Canal	4	1958
6	Chichonki Malian	Sheikhupura, Punjab	Run of Canal	13	1959
7	Warsak	Peshawar, KPK	Run of River	243	1960
8	Shadiwal	Shadiwal Warriach, Punjab	Run of Canal	14	1961
9	Nandipur	Gujranwala, Punjab	Run of Canal	14	1963
10	Mangla	Mirpur, Azad Kashmir	Reservoir	1000	1967
11	Chitral	Chitral, KPK	Run of Canal	1	1975
12	Tarbela	Tarbela, KPK	Reservoir	3478	1977
13	Chashma	Chashma, Punjab	Run of River	184	2000
14	Jagran	Neelum, Azad Kashmir	Hydro	30	2000
15	Ghazi-Barotha	Attock, Punjab	Run of River	1450	2003
16	Malakan-III	Malakand, KPK	Run of River/Canal	81	2008
17	Khan Khwar	Shangla, KPK	Reservoir	72	2010
18	Pehur	Swabi, KPK	Canal Fall/Run of River	18	2010
19	Jinnah	Jinnah Barrage, Punjab	Run of River	96	2012
20	Garam Chashma	Chitral, KPK	Hydro	1	2012
21	Allai Khwar	Mansehra, KPK	Reservoir	121	2013
22	Gomal Zam	South Waziristan	Reservoir	17	2013
23	Laraib Energy	Jhelum River, AJ&K	Hydro	84	2013
24	Duber Khwar	Kohistan, KPK	Reservoir	130	2014
25	Patrind Hydro	Muzaffarabad, Azad Kashmir	Run of River	147	2017
26	Golen Gol	Chitral, KPK	Run of River	108	2018

Annex 9 . Installed and Under Construction Hydro Power Stations in Pakistan Source: NEPRA (2021)

	STATION	LOCATION	Type	CAPACITY (MW)	Year in Service
27	Neelum-Jhelum	Muzaffarabad, Azad Kashmir	Run of River	969	2018
28	Marala-Hydro (PPDCL)	Sialkot, Punjab	Canal Fall/Run of River	8	2018
29	Tarbela 4th Ext.	Tarbela, KPK	Reservoir	1410	2019
30	Gulpur Hydro	Gulpur, Azad Kashmir	Run of River	101	2020
31	Daral Khwar	Swat District, KPK	Run of River	37	2021
32	Ranolia	Kohistan, KPK	High Head	17	2021
33	Karot	AJK, Punjab	Run of River	720	2022
<i>Under Construction</i>					
	STATION	LOCATION		CAPACITY (MW)	
1	Keyal Khwar	Lower Kohistan, Khyber Paktunkhwa		72	
2	Dasu	Dasu Town		4320	
3	Tarbela 5th Ext.	Tarbela, KPK		1410	
4	Mohmand	Mohmand Tribal District, KP		800	
5	Diamer Basha	Near Chilas, KP & GB		4500	
6	Kurram Tangi	North Waziristan, KP		83	
7	Kurram Tangi	Mansehra, KP		884	
8	Mangla Refurbishment Project	Minpur, Azad Kashmir		310	

Annex 10 . Installed and Under Construction Wind Power Stations in Pakistan Source: NEPRA (2021)

	STATION	LOCATION	CAPACITY (MW)	Year in Service
1	FFC Energy	Jhimpir, Sindh	49.5	2013
2	Zorlu Energy Pakistan (Pvt.) Ltd	Jhimpir, Sindh	56.4	2013
3	Three Gorges First Wind Farm Pakistan (Pvt.) Ltd	Jhimpir, Sindh	49.5	2014
4	Foundation Wind Energy - II Ltd.	Gharo, Sindh	50	2015
5	Foundation Wind Energy - I Ltd.	Gharo, Sindh	50	2015
6	Sapphire Wind Power Company Ltd	Jhimpir, Sindh	52.8	2015
7	Yunus Energy Ltd	Jhimpir, Sindh	50	2015
8	Metro Wind Power Co Ltd	Jhimpir, Sindh	50	2016
9	Tapal Wind Energy Pvt. Ltd	Jhimpir, Sindh	30	2016
10	Tenega Generai Ltd	Gharo, Sindh	49.5	2016
11	Master Wind Energy Ltd	Jhimpir, Sindh	52.8	2016
12	Gul Wind Energy Ltd	Jhimpir, Sindh	50	2016
13	HydroChina Dawood Wind Power Project	Gharo, Sindh	49.5	2017
14	Sachal Energy Wind Farm	Jhimpir, Sindh	50	2017
15	United Energy Pakistan Wind Ltd	Jhimpir, Sindh	99	2017
16	Hawa Energy Ltd	Jhimpir, Sindh	49.6	2018
17	Jhampir Wind Power Ltd	Jhimpir, Sindh	49.7	2018
18	Artistic Energy Pvt. Ltd	Jhimpir, Sindh	49.3	2018
19	Three Gorges Second Wind Farm Pakistan (Pvt.) Ltd	Jhimpir, Sindh	49.5	2018
20	Three Gorges Third Wind Farm Pakistan (Pvt.) Ltd	Jhimpir, Sindh	49.5	2018
21	Burj Capital Jhimpir Wind Power Limited	Jhimpir, Sindh	50	2018
22	Tricon Boston Consulting Corporation Pvt. Ltd (A)	Jhimpir, Sindh	49.6	2018
23	Tricon Boston Consulting Corporation Pvt. Ltd (B)	Jhimpir, Sindh	49.6	2018
24	Zephyr Power Ltd	Gharo, Sindh	50	2019
25	Master Green Energy Pvt Ltd	Jhimpir, Sindh	50	2021
26	Tricon Wind Power Pvt. Ltd.	Jhimpir, Sindh	50	2021

Annex 11 . Installed Biomass Power Stations in Pakistan Source: NEPRA (2021)

	STATION	LOCATION	CAPACITY (MW)
1	Jamal Din Wali-II	Rahim Yar Khan, Punjab	26
2	Jamal Din Wali-III	Rahim Yar Khan, Punjab	27
3	RYK Mills	Rahim Yar Khan, Punjab	40
4	Chiniot Power	Chiniot, Punjab	63
5	Fatima Energy	Muzzaffargarh, Punjab	120
6	Hamza Sugar Mills	Rahim Yar Khan, Punjab	15
7	The Thal Industries Corporation	Layyah, Punjab	20
8	Almoiz Industries	Mianwali, Punjab	36
9	Chanar Energy	Faisalabad, Punjab	22

Annex 12. Installed and Under Construction Solar Power Stations in Pakistan Source: NEPRA (2021)

	STATION	LOCATION	CAPACITY (MW)
1	Quaid-e-Azam Solar Park	Bahawalpur, Punjab	100
2	Appolo Solar Development	Bahawalpur, Punjab	100
3	Best Green Energy	Bahawalpur, Punjab	100
4	Crest Energy	Bahawalpur, Punjab	100
5	AJ Power Pvt Ltd	Khushab, Punjab	12
6	Harappa Solar Pvt Ltd	Sahiwal, Punjab	18
7	Orsun Pakistan	Thatta, Sindh	50
8	Gharo Solar	Thatta, Sindh	50
<i>Under Construction</i>			
	STATION	LOCATION	CAPACITY (MW)
1	Zhenfa Pakistan New Energy Company (Pvt.) Limited	Layyah	100
2	Meridian Energy (Pvt) Ltd	Sukkur, Sindh	50
3	HND Energy (Pvt) Ltd	Sukkur, Sindh	60
4	Helios Power (Pvt) Ltd	Sukkur, Sindh	50
5	Quaid-e-Azam Solar Park	Bahawalpur, Punjab	400

Pakistan is proven to have fuel reserves of its own as seen in Annex 13. Renewable energy potential generation data (Annex 14) was retrieved from governmental reports and previous studies, all taking not account “achievable energy generation given system performance, topographic, environmental, and land-use constraints” (NREL).

Annex 13. Proven domestic fuel reserves

Fuels	Proven Reserves	Source
Crude Oil (billion barrels)	0.54	(EIA, 2021)
Coal (million tonnes)	3063.9	(EIA, 2022a)
Natural Gas (trillion cubic metres)	0.536	(EIA, 2022b)

Annex 14. Estimated renewable energy potential generation

Technology	Potential Generation (MW)	Source
Solar PV	2,900,000	(Rafique, Rehman, and Alhems, 2020)
Wind	346,000	(Ahmad <i>et al.</i> , 2016)
Offshore Wind	21,000	(World Bank, 2020)
Hydropower	60,000	(WAPDA, 2019)
Small Hydropower	9,507	(PCRET, 2020)
Geothermal	240,000	(Younas <i>et al.</i> , 2016)

Demand Projection

Electricity demand projection (Annex 15) was based on final consumption and energy balance data retrieved from the IEA Sankey Diagram (Annexes 16 and 18). Similarly, demand data forecast from the Government of Pakistan IEP Report (2022) was also considered (Annex 17).

Annex 15. Electricity Demand Data

Demand (PJ)	2015	2020	2025	2030	2040	2050	2060	2070
Industrial electricity demand	94.58273	112.3806	133.5274	158.2995	222.4834	312.6912	439.4803	617.6794
Residential electricity demand	180.5534	214.5285	254.8968	302.1854	424.7091	596.9109	838.9445	1179.117
Commercial electricity demand	52.57092	62.46331	74.21715	87.98595	123.6606	173.7998	244.2717	343.3182
Total	327.70705	389.37241	462.64135	548.47085	770.8531	1083.4019	1522.6965	2140.1146

Annex 16. Final Consumption Data (Mtoe) Source: IEA Sankey Diagram for Pakistan

Fuel	2015	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
COAL	4.91	10.61	12.7	14.93	17.70	21.00	24.91	29.56
OIL	17.5	18.13	22.97	26.78	32.54	39.55	48.07	58.43
GAS	18.15	17.78	18.17	19.5	20.42	21.38	22.39	23.45
ELECTRICITY	7.78	9.3	11.05	13.1	15.54	18.45	21.90	25.99

Annex 17. Demand Data (Mtoe) Source: GoP IEP Report (2021)

Fuel	2015	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
COAL	8.863945	10.61	12.7	14.93	17.55157	20.63346	24.2565	28.51571
OIL	14.30983	18.13	22.97	26.78	31.22196	36.4007	42.43843	49.47763
GAS	17.39837	17.78	18.17	19.5	20.92735	22.45918	24.10314	25.86743
ELECTRICITY	7.827149	9.3	11.05	13.1	15.53032	18.41151	21.82722	25.87661

Annex 18. Energy Balance Final Consumption Source: IEA Sankey Diagram for Pakistan

Final Consumption (PJ)	2015	2016	2017	2018	Average
Industry Oil Products	84.6	82	75.7	55.7	74.5
Industry Biofuels & Waste	153.7	157	160.3	163.6	158.65
Industry Coal	205.7	238.4	313.9	367	281.25
Industry Electricity	90.1	86.4	98.9	103.5	94.725
Industry NGS	274.5	313.6	303.9	257.7	287.425
Transport Oil Products	566.4	635.5	699	642.4	635.825
Transport Biofuels & Waste	0	0	0	0	0
Transport Coal	0	0	0	0	0
Transport Electricity	0	0	0	0	0
Transport NGS	60	62.6	65.6	60.6	62.2
Residential Oil Products	22.7	24	25.4	22.9	23.75
Residential Biofuels & Waste	1231.4	1257.3	1283.7	1310.4	1270.7
Residential Coal	0	0	0	0	0
Residential Electricity	160.2	175.3	194.5	193.3	180.825
Residential NGS	252.6	270.8	264.8	290.3	269.625
Commerce Oil Products	28.2	28.1	31.9	27.2	28.85
Commerce Biofuels & Waste	0	0	0	0	0
Commerce Coal	0	0	0	0	0
Commerce Electricity	44.6	49	55.1	61.9	52.65
Commerce NGS	31.3	30.6	29.9	29	30.2

Scenario Configuration Assumptions

Least Cost Scenario (LC)

The *Least Cost (LC)* scenario assumes there will be no new policy interventions in the energy sector and models the most cost-effective way to meet demand and can't therefore be considered as a BAU scenario. Its utility proves efficient when comparing results with other scenarios modelled under specific policies and targets. Constraints were applied and maintained in the *FF* and *NZ* scenarios for consistency. Reduced timeslices (from 96 to 8) have been applied to increase the speed of model operation and to reflect the level of energy data granularity available for Pakistan. Also, technologies and commodities required to meet transport demand have been removed as including these produced results with a much higher fossil fuel capacity to fulfil a higher power demand than is possible in Pakistan. The technology that represents transmission imports in the power sector (PWRTRNIMP) has also been removed to investigate how Pakistan will meet electricity demand domestically.

Fossil Future Scenario (FF)

The *Fossil Future (FF)* scenario was based on the *LC* scenario with all new capital investment into renewable energy technologies throughout the entire modelling period constrained to zero. In other words, the model is constrained to only invest in fossil fuel technologies.

Net Zero Scenario by 2050 (NZ)

Historical CO₂ emissions between 2015 and 2019 are used to calculate the average percentage increase of emissions, then extrapolated to peak in 2030 before reaching a linear decrease to 0 by 2050. Based on this, the *Net Zero by 2050 (NZ)* scenario constrains the maximum capacity investment for primary fossil fuel and biomass production technologies, as well as nuclear. Activity of renewable technology is then projected to meet demand.

Model Assumptions

Within the model, if specific input data cannot be sourced at the national level, certain parameters, such as the capacity factors for power plants, have been assumed by the researcher to be similar to other South Asian countries and sourced from international organisations such as the IEA and IRENA.

OSeMOSYS also considers 2070 as the end of the world as the last timeslice due to the model's preparation to cease production in the last year of the modelling period (2070). This suggests that the model results for 2070 may not be an accurate representation of reality and should be approached with caution.

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